

APECS Annual Report 2016-2017

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The **APECS Annual Report 2016-2017** was compiled by the APECS International Directorate Office based on information reported by the APECS committees, project groups and National Committees.

For more information on **APECS** go to: www.apecs.is

For more information on the **APECS National Committees** go to: <https://www.apecs.is/get-involved/national-committees.html>

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APECS International Directorate Office

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Executive Summary

Thank you for taking the time to read the 2016-2017 APECS annual report. Inside you will find a wealth of information about what APECS has accomplished over this last year.

This has been an exciting year for APECS, full of changes big and small. Our membership continues to grow around the world, as new national committees formed in Argentina and South Africa. The APECS Council was larger this year than ever before, reflecting a diversity of nationalities, career stages, and research interests.

Perhaps the biggest change for APECS this year was the Secretariat office moving from Tromsø, Norway to Potsdam, Germany. We extend great thanks to the Research Council of Norway and the University of Tromsø for their longtime support of the Secretariat. Without their help, APECS could not have become the organization it is today. The Alfred Wegener Institute has kindly agreed to host us starting in February, 2017, and now our Secretariat has settled into our wonderful new home.

In 2016, with input from our members, advisors, alumni, and national committees, APECS developed a strategic plan. This year, we set to work implementing that strategic plan. The first big change was a shift from Council being made up of three large committees (Research Activities, Education & Outreach, and Member Engagement) to a model in which individual project groups were convened within the Council. This allowed our Council members to focus more on their areas of interest and set up a mechanism by which projects that were no longer necessary could be wrapped up. Already, this structure has facilitated members taking on leadership positions within the Council.

This year marks the 10th anniversary of APECS as an organization. It has been an opportunity for us to look back on our history as an organization and marvel at everything that we have accomplished. APECS has reached approximately 8,000 members over the years, held well over 100 events, and recorded more than 200 webinars. We have developed excellent relationships with many partner organizations, relationships that help create opportunities for early career researchers.

If the last ten years have taught us anything, it is that incredible things can happen when our members take on projects. I want to take this opportunity to thank our members and leadership for their hard work this year, our mentors for their thoughtful advice, our partner organizations and sponsors for their ongoing support, and our host institutions for their incredible dedication to making sure early career researchers around the world have opportunities to contribute to the polar community.

I hope you are inspired by this report. We look forward to the next ten years!

Alice Bradley
APECS President 2016-2017

1. Organizational Overview

1.1. APECS Leadership

The APECS leadership is comprised of early career researchers that are interested in and committed to furthering the activities and the future directions of the organization. An Executive Committee and a Council lead the organization, supported by the international Directorate.

APECS Executive Committee 2016 - 2017		
APECS President	Alice Bradley <i>Dartmouth College, USA</i>	
APECS Vice-Presidents	Dr. Josefine Lenz <i>Alfred Wegener Institute, Helmholtz Center for Polar and Marine Research / University of Alaska Fairbanks, Germany / USA</i>	Hanne Nielsen <i>University of Tasmania, Australia</i>
	Alexander Thornton <i>University of Alaska Fairbanks, USA</i>	TJ Young <i>University of Cambridge, UK</i>
Ex-officios	Dr. Heather Mariash <i>National Wildlife Research Centre, Canada</i>	Dr. Ruth Vingerhagen <i>University of Cambridge, UK</i>
	Dr. Trista Vick-Majors <i>Montana State University, UK</i>	
Temporary*	Jean Holloway <i>University of Ottawa, Canada</i>	Tamara Fletcher <i>University of Montana, USA</i>

*filling in during longer periods of absence of Executive Committee Members

Figure 1: APECS Executive Committee 2016-2017: TJ Young, Josefine Lenz, Alice Bradley, Gerlis Fugmann, Heike Midleja (front row, left to right); Alex Thornton, Hanne Nielsen, Ruth

APECS Council 2016 - 2017

Council Chairs

Gabriela Roldan

Gateway Antarctica / University of Canterbury, New Zealand

Lorna Thurston

Northern Arizona University, USA

National Committee Coordinators

Jilda Caccavo

University of Padua, Italy

Sara Strey

Northland College, USA

Council Members

Inhye Ahn

Korean Polar Research Institute, South Korea

Devsamridhi Arora

University of Delhi / Indian Polar Research Network (IPRN), India

Sara Aparicio

European Space Agency / APECS Portugal, Italy / Portugal

Mia Bennett

UCLA / USAPECS, USA

Ted Bibby

University of North Dakota, USA

Gesche Blume-Werry

Umea University, Sweden

Bruce Boles

University of Tennessee, USA

Liz Bowman

ARCUS, USA

Julie Bull

University of Victoria, Canada

Francois Burgay

CA' Foscari University of Venice / APECS Italy, Italy

Marta Bystrowska

University of Silesia / APECS Poland, Poland

Adam Campbell

University of Otago, New Zealand

Elizabeth Ceperley

University of Wisconsin-Madison, USA

Nicolas Champollion

International Space Science Institute / University of Bremen / APECS Switzerland, Germany / Switzerland

Henrik Christiansen

KU Leuven / APECS Belgium, Belgium

Caroline Coch

Alfred Wegener Institute, Helmholtz Center for Polar and Marine Research / APECS Germany, Germany

Jennifer Cooper

California State University Los Angeles / University of California Irvine, USA

Adrian Dahood

George Mason University, USA

Archana Dayal

University of Sheffield / UK Polar Network, UK

Meagan Dewar

Deakin University / APECS Oceania, Australia

Onur Sabri Durak

Istanbul Technical University / APECS Turkey, Turkey

Tamara Fletcher

University of Montana, USA

Friederike Gehrmann

University of Helsinki / APECS Finland, Finland

Caroline Geisert

ENSTA Bretagne, France

Vikram Goel

Norwegian Polar Institute, Norway

Claire Griffin

University of Minnesota - Twin Cities, USA

Maxim Gutenev <i>South Ural States University, Russia</i>	Christel Hansen <i>Rhodes University / APECS South Africa, South Africa</i>
Laura Hobbs <i>University of Strathclyde / Scottish Association of Marine Science / UK Polar Network, UK</i>	Jean Holloway <i>University of Ottawa, Canada</i>
Christopher Horvat <i>Harvard University, USA</i>	Luis Huckstadt <i>University of California Santa Cruz, USA</i>
Bruno Ibanez <i>Universidad Peruana Cayetano Heredia / APECS Peru, Peru</i>	Shridhar Jawak <i>National Centre for Antarctic and Ocean Research, India</i>
Lynn Kaluziński <i>University of Maine, USA</i>	Hanna Maria Kauko <i>Norwegian Polar Institute, Norway</i>
Minkyung Kim <i>Seoul National University, South Korea</i>	Nikita Kuprikov <i>Russian Polar Initiative, Russia</i>
Olivia Lee <i>University of Alaska Fairbanks, USA</i>	Lydie Lescaumontier <i>Australian National University / APECS France, France</i>
Douwe Maat <i>Netherlands Institute for Sea Research / APECS Netherlands, Netherlands</i>	Sebastian Marinsek <i>Instituto Antartico Argentino / APECS Argentina, Argentina</i>
Claudia Maturana <i>Universidad de Chile / APECS Chile, Chile</i>	Kyle Mayers <i>National Oceanography Centre Southampton / University of Southampton / UK Polar Network, UK</i>
Bernabé Moreno <i>Científica del Sur University / APECS Peru, Peru</i>	Swati Nagar <i>National Centre for Antarctic and Ocean Research, India</i>
Karolina Paquin <i>Freelancing, Norway / Svalbard</i>	Igor Stelmach Pessi <i>University of Liège / APECS Belgium, Belgium</i>
José Queirós <i>University of Coimbra, Portugal</i>	Corinna Röver <i>KTH Royal Institute of Technology, Sweden</i>
Pablo Rodríguez Ros <i>Institut de Ciències des Mar (ICM-CSIC), Spain</i>	Vicki Sahanatien <i>APECS Canada, Canada</i>
Vincent Schulze <i>Global and European Studies Institute Leipzig, Germany</i>	José Seco <i>University of Aveiro / University of St. Andrews / APECS Portugal, Portugal / UK</i>
Elisa Seyboth <i>Universidade Federal do Rio Grande-FURG / APECS Brazil, Brazil</i>	Evgeniia Sidorova <i>University of Calgary, Canada</i>
Neelu Singh <i>National Centre for Antarctic and Ocean Research, India</i>	Runa A. Skarbo <i>The Norwegian University of Science and Technology, Norway</i>
Merran Smith <i>Yukon Government, Canada</i>	Andrea Spolaor <i>CA' Foscari University of Venice / APECS Italy, Italy</i>
Alison Thieffry <i>Laval University, Canada</i>	Ekaterina Uryupova <i>University of Salford, UK</i>

Gary Wesche
Polar Educators International, USA

Nadya Yanakieva
Sofia University "St. Kliment Ohridski" / APECS Bulgaria, Bulgaria

Scott Zolkos
University of Alberta, Canada

Ex-officio

Yulia Zaika
Khibiny educational and scientific base, M.V. Lomonosov Moscow State University / APECS Russia, Russia

1.2. APECS International Directorate Office

The APECS International Directorate is the essential coordinating body without which the organization and running of the various APECS activities and programmes would hardly be possible and APECS is grateful for the continued support provided by its Directorate sponsors.

a) Main locations:

Until January 2017, the APECS International Directorate with an Executive Director was funded by the generous support of the Research Council of Norway, UiT The Arctic University of Norway and the Norwegian Polar Institute. The

position was housed at UiT at the Faculty of Biosciences, Fisheries and Economics in **Tromsø, Norway**. All three sponsors had funded the position for APECS already since 2009 and APECS wants to sincerely thank them for this tremendous support that really was key for allowing our organization to grow and develop into what it is today.

From February 2017, the APECS International Directorate moved to the Alfred Wegener Institute, Helmholtz Center for Polar and Marine Research in **Potsdam Germany** and is generously funded with two positions (Executive Director and Administrative Assistant). The current funding agreement is place **until January 2022**.

b) Other location:

From **July 2016 until February 2017**, Murmansk Arctic State University, funded a part-time **APECS Officer** for the APECS International Directorate located in **Murmansk, Russia**.

APECS International Directorate		
Executive Director	Dr. Gerlis Fugmann* Alfred Wegener Institute, Helmholtz Centre for Polar and Marine Research / UiT The Arctic University of Norway, Norway	
Administrative Assistant	Heike Midleja (since February 2017)** Alfred Wegener Institute, Helmholtz Center for Polar and Marine Research, Germany	
APECS Officer	Yulia Sultanbayeva (July 2016 until February 2017)*** Murmansk Arctic State University, Russia	

* funded full-time through until January 2017 by the Research Council of Norway, UiT The Arctic University of Norway, Norwegian Polar Institute, Norway. From February 2017 funded full-time by the Alfred Wegener Institute, Helmholtz Center for Polar and Marine Research (Germany)

** funded part-time through the Alfred Wegener Institute, Helmholtz Center for Polar and Marine Research (Germany) since February 2017

*** funded part-time through Murmansk Arctic State University, Russia, from July 2016 until February 2017

1.3. APECS National Committees

To better respond to the needs of specific countries, APECS has National Committees (NCs), which are linked to and a vital part of the international APECS network. Some countries have well implemented national committees, whereas others are just getting started. APECS has currently 25 active NC's working at the national level with locally based early career scientists (ECS's). In addition, a number of other countries keep active mailing lists or social media profiles but are not formal committees at the moment. Find out more about the [APECS National Committee](#) and how to contact them on the [APECS website](#).

APECS National Committee Leaderships 2016-2017

APECS Argentina	Sebastián Marinsek (Instituto Antártico Argentino)
APECS Belgium	Sophie Berger (Université Libre de Bruxelles); Henrik Christiansen (KU Leuven); Alexandra Gossart (KU Leuven); Francesca Pasotti (Universiteit Gent); Igor S. Pessi (Université de Liège); Eveline Pinseel (Universiteit Gent); Arnout Roukaerts (Vrije Universiteit Brussel)
APECS Brazil (Associação de Pesquisadores educadores em Início de Carreira sobre o Mar e os Polos)	Juliana Assunção Ivar do Sul (President); Juliana Silva Souza (Vice-President); Adriana R. de Lira Pessoa (1a Secretariat); Ana Olivia de A. Reis (2a Secretariat); Douglas Lindemann (Treasurer); Fernanda Quaglio (Scientific Coordinator); Roberta da Cruz Piuco (E&O Coordinator); Erli Schneider Costa (1a Project Development Coordinator); Gerusa Radichi (2a Project development Coordinator); Silvia Dotta (1a Graduate related Actions Coordinator); Claudineia Lizieri (2a Graduate related Actions Coordinator); Thiago Severo (Fund-raising Coordinator)
APECS Bulgaria	Iglika Trifonova (Bulgarian Antarctic Institute), Denitsa Apostolova (Sofia University), Asparuh Kamburov (University of Mining and Geology “St. Ivan Rilski”)
APECS Chile	Claudia Maturana (University of Chile), Javier Naretto (University of Chile), Jose Araos (Universidad Alberto Hurtado); Sebastian Ruiz (Pontificia Universidad Católica de Chile);

APECS Canada	Tonya Burgers (Communications Working Group), Vladislav Petrusevich (Website Working Group), Ann Balasubramaniam (Communications Coordinator, Website Working Group), Marianne Falardeau-Cote (Mentor Award Working Group, Website Working Group), Meagan Grabowski (Chair APECS Canada (March-present), Website Working Group, APECS Council), Marney Paradis (Chair APECS Canada (October-March), Chair of Mentor Award Working Group), Kristen Peck (board member), Pascale Ropars (board member), Vicki Sahanatien (National Committee Representative on APECS Council, APECS-Canada Representative on Science and Technology Advisory Committee of Polar Knowledge Canada), Evgennii (Jenn) Sidorova (board member), Nicolaus Ganter (Ex-Officio)
APECS France	Céline Clément-Chastel (President), Mathieu Gesta (Vice-president), Lydie Lescarmontier (Vice-president), Sophie Shiavone (Secretary), Veronique Dansereau (Treasurer)
APECS Germany	Andreas Preußner (Chair) (University of Trier / ILTS Sapporo); Josefine Lenz (Co-Chair) (Alfred Wegener Institute Potsdam; University of Alaska Fairbanks); Stefanie Arndt (Co-Chair) (Alfred Wegener Institute, Bremerhaven); Johanna Grabow (Co-Chair) (University of Leipzig); Caroline Coch (Alfred Wegener Institute Potsdam); Heike Link (University of Rostock); Stefanie Weege (German Research Centre for Geosciences Potsdam); Liv Heinecke (Alfred Wegener Institute Potsdam); Christian Katlein (Alfred Wegener Institute Bremerhaven); Svenja Halfter ; Kathrin Keil (Institute for Advanced Sustainability Studies Potsdam); Tim Carlsen (University of Leipzig); Vincent Schulze (University of Berlin)
Indian Polar Research Network	Devsamridhi Arora (University of Delhi); Anant Pandey (Wildlife Institute of India); Swati Nagar (National Centre for Antarctic and Ocean Research)
APECS Italy	François Burgay (University of Venice Ca'Foscari); Jilda Alicia Caccavo (University of Padua); Federico Dallo (University of Venice Ca'Foscari); Andrea Spolaor (University of Venice Ca'Foscari)
APECS Japan	Shunsuke Tei (Hokkaido University), Shun Tsutaki (Japan Aerospace Exploration Agency), Daiki Sakakibara (Hokkaido University), Naoya Kanna (Hokkaido University), Kazuki Nakata (Japan Aerospace Exploration Agency).
APECS Netherlands	Douwe Maat (Netherlands Institute for Sea Research), Sebastiaan Kopelle (curr. no affil.)
APECS Oceania (Australia and New Zealand)	Hanne Nielsen (University of Tasmania, Australia), Gabriela Roldan (University of Canterbury, New Zealand), Jasmine Lee (The University of Queensland, Australia), Meagan Dewar (Federation University, Deakin University, Australia)
APECS Peru	Bruno Ibañez (NC) , Bernabe Moreno (NC)
APECS Poland	Maja Lisowska (University of Silesia); Marta Bystrowska (University of Silesia)
APECS Portugal	Sara Aparício (European Space Agency), Filipa Carvalho (Rutgers University); José Seco (University of Aveiro); José Queirós (MARE Marine and Environmental Sciences Centre)
Polar Initiative (Russia)	Russian Polar Initiative Leadership: Ivan Dubinenkov - NGO Polar Initiative, Nikita Kuprikov - Moscow Aviation Institute / NGO Polar Initiative, Alexey Pavlov (Norwegian Polar Institute) ; Russian National Committee Board: Alexey Pavlov (Norwegian Polar Institute), Ivan Dubinenkov (MSU, AWI, RPI), Alina Karpova (SPSU), Nikita Kuprikov (MAI University, RPI), Denis Doronin (VNIIOKEANLOGII), Konstantin Zaykov (consulting member, Arctic director NARFU), Anna Scherbina (consulting member, RAS early career committee member, President of Russian early career

	<p>scientist union), Gleb Kraev (RAS, PYRN Russia, APECS member), Danila Zhuravskiy (RPI), Svetlana Marich (consulting member, Kenozersky National Park), Alex Nikolshin (consulting member, RUDN University student, VP for Russian youth engineers union)</p>
APECS Russia	<p>E.Uryupova (APECS Council); P.Konstantinov (Moscow State University), Y.Zaika (Khibiny research station)</p>
APECS South Africa	<p>Christel Hansen (APECSSA Chair) (Rhodes University (RSA)); Marius Rossouw (APECSSA Co-Chair) (Stellenbosch University (RSA)); Liesel Rudolph (APECSSA Organizational Liaison) (University of the Free State (RSA)); Rosie Dwight (APECSSA Outreach Coordinator) (Texas A&M University (USA))</p>
APECS Sweden	<p>Patrícia Pečnerová (Swedish Museum of Natural History) (2016 executive secretary); Céline Heuzé (University of Gothenburg) (2017 executive secretary); Corinna Röver (KTH) (2017 NC representative); Mats Björkman (University of Gothenburg); Matthias Siewert and Juri Palmtag (Stockholm University); Joachim Jansen (KTH); Rhiannon Mondav (University of Uppsala); Lorna Little (SMHI)</p>
APECS Switzerland	<p>Saskia Gindraux - Swiss Federal Institute for Forest, Snow and Landscape Research WSL; Anneli Strobel (University of Basel).</p>
APECS Turkey	<p>Burcu Ozsoy - ITU Polar Research Center (ITU PolReC), Ozgun Oktar - ITU Polar Research Center (ITU PolReC), Dogac Baybars Isiler, Deniz Vural, Sinan Yirmibesoglu</p>
UK Polar Network	<p>Leadership Committee: Kyle Mayers (President) (National Oceanography Centre), TJ Young (Vice-President) (University of Cambridge); Sammie Buzzard (Vice-President) (University of Reading), Elaine Mawbey (Treasurer) (University of Bristol), Andrew Williamson (Treasurer) (University of Cambridge), Archana Dayal (Secretary) (University of Sheffield), Patrizia Isabella Duda (Secretary) (University College London); Education and Outreach Committee: Jenny Turton (Head) (British Antarctic Survey & University of Leeds), Maddie Brasier (University of Liverpool & the National Oceanographic Centre), Michelle McCrystall (British Antarctic Survey & University of Cambridge). Thomas Dowling, Malu Avila (Freelance Science and Editorial Consultant, Polar Expert), Harriet Clewlow (British Antarctic Survey, University of Exeter, and WWF); Sam Black (University of Copenhagen); APECS Representative: Laura Hobbs (Scottish Association of Marine Sciences); NCAR Representative: Amber Leeson (University of Lancaster); Social Media Members: Julia Feuer-Cotter (University of Nottingham), Estanislao Gavilan Pascual-Ahuir, Georgia Hole (Oxford University), Christine Jones, Kirstie Jones-Williams (British Antarctic Survey); Members-at-large: Chelsey Baker (University of Southampton), Anna Belcher (University of Southampton), Ella Darlington (Loughborough University), Eleanor Jones (University of Sheffield), Ruth Vingerhagen (University of Cambridge)</p>
US APECS (United States)	<p>Alex Thornton (Co-Chair) (University of Alaska Fairbanks); Ellyn Enderlin (Co-Chair, Project Lead) (University of Maine); Alice Bradley (Former Co-Chair) (Dartmouth College); Mia Bennett (Outreach Project Lead) (University of California Los Angeles); Olivia Lee (Alaska/PNW Rep.) (University of Alaska Fairbanks); Jeff Bowman (Organizational Liaison); Ted Bibby; Jim Crowell (Arizona State University); Sara Strey; David Schutt</p>

1.4. APECS Membership 2017

The current membership of APECS are 2762 from 66 countries.¹ The Top 5 countries of 66 total in membership numbers in APECS -representing 50.4 percent of the total active APECS membership are: 1) United States, 2) Canada, 3) United Kingdom, 4) Germany, and 5) Norway.

The gender information shows that 58.18 percent of APECS members are female and 40.62 percent male. Master and Doctoral Students as well as Postdoctoral Researchers represent combined 68.35 percent of APECS members. The career level of the remaining members includes undergraduate students, research scientists, faculty members, teachers and others.

Figure 1: Countries with APECS National Committees (orange) and APECS members (blue) (data as of 16 September 2017)

APECS traditionally represents members that are conducting research in the Polar Regions, which also shows in the regional focus selections made: 53.62 percent stated they are involved in Antarctic research and 71.72 percent are involved in Arctic research. It should be noted that 31.93 percent of the members selected both Arctic and Antarctic. Also, 21.54 percent are involved in Alpine research, and about 12.56 percent in research in the Himalaya and 9.8 percent in other regions of the world. Multiple answers were possible for this question.

The member registration form also allows members to provide information on the regional focus of their research as well as the research disciplines they represent, with the ability to select multiple answers. Figure 3 shows the research disciplines and percentage of members that selected them.

Figure 2: A distribution of disciplines of APECS members, with environmental sciences, ecology, geosciences, cryology / glaciology and oceanography being the top 5 fields represented by APECS members.

¹ Number as of 16 September 2017

2. The 10th Anniversary of APECS

APECS was celebrating its 10th anniversary in 2017! Since its inception during the International Polar Year 2007-2008, APECS has been widely recognized as one of the legacies of the IPY continuing to provide networking, training and career development opportunities for early career researchers as well as promoting education and outreach as integral components of polar research.

This year, as part of the 10th anniversary celebrations of our flourishing organization, we invited members to design an APECS logo featuring this milestone, with the winning logo to be used on all official items authored during 2017. The winner was the design by **Stephanie Bates**, a research technician at the **University of Bristol (United Kingdom)** specialising in isotope biogeochemistry.

What has happened in the last 10 years?

Figure 4: APECS Executive Committee 2007-2008 in Iceland after writing the APECS constitution

An idea developed by our three co-founders Jenny Baeseman, Hugues Lantuit and Rhian Salmon has developed from a small, dedicated group during the 4th International Polar Year (IPY) 2007-2008 to a global community. Over the last decade, more than 7130 early career researchers and professionals from 102 different countries joined the APECS network. In December 2017 at the time of writing this report, we had 2971 subscribed members from 66 countries.

Our activities in APECS depend on the help of many volunteers around the world that are engaged both on the international and national level. Just the APECS international leadership (Council, Executive Committee and International Directorate) alone included 218 early career researchers from 30 countries on 5 continents since 2007 (see Fig. 5). The gender ratio shows that a majority of those, 64 percent were female early career researchers. In addition to the international leadership many more volunteers helped within our APECS National Committees and individual projects.

Our activities in APECS depend on the help of many volunteers around the world that are engaged both on the international and national level. Just the APECS international leadership (Council, Executive Committee and International Directorate) alone included 218 early career researchers from 30 countries on 5 continents since 2007 (see Fig. 5). The gender ratio shows that a majority of those, 64 percent were female early career researchers. In addition to the international leadership many more volunteers helped within our APECS National Committees and individual projects.

A detailed listing all of the members of the [APECS Executive Committees](#) and [APECS Councils](#) since the start of our organization can be found on the APECS website.

Crucial to the success of APECS was the establishment of an International Directorate Office for the organisation with one full-time Executive Director and since February 2017 also with a part-time Administrative Assistant. The APECS International Directorate Members since the start of our organization are listed on the [APECS website](#). We want to thank here specifically the main institutions that provided support for our office over the last decade:

Figure 5: Countries around the world represented by APECS leadership members since 2007

- January 2009 until December 2016 in Tromsø (Norway): **Research Council of Norway**, the UiT The University of Tromsø and the Norwegian Polar Institute. In 2010 and 2011 we also received funding support through the Tromsø Kommune. And from June 2016 to February 2017, Murmansk Arctic State University (Russia) funded an additional part-time APECS Officer for our secretariat.

- February 2017 until January 2022: Alfred Wegener Institute, Helmholtz Centre for Polar and Marine Research will be supporting the main APECS International Directorate until January 2022.

Figure 6: Some of the APECS Executive Committees during their in-person meetings in the last 10 years. From top left to right:

APECS Executive Committee **2015-2016**;
 APECS Executive Committee **2011-2012**;
 APECS Executive Committee **2016-2017**;
 APECS Executive Committee **2010-2011**;
 APECS Executive Committee **2014-2015**;
 APECS Executive Committee **2015-2016**;
 APECS Executive Committee **2013-2014**

It is impossible to list all activities and resources that APECS developed in its first 10 years as this would fill a huge report. If you are interested in finding out more about our activities over the years, we encourage you to read the APECS Annual Reports that are available since 2008 here. Here just a few highlights:

- 117 reported workshops as well as 90 panels / townhall meetings / roundtables organized by APECS and its National Committees in 33 countries
- More than 130 webinars organized since 2010 and available through the APECS Webinar Archive
- Many Education and Outreach events for International Polar Weeks (since 2012) and Antarctica Days (since 2011)
- A variety of resources available on our website e.g. Job Board, Event List, Mentorship Database, Funding Database
- Successful projects initiated by APECS or where APECS was and is a partner on such as the the APECS Virtual Poster Session (2010 - 2012), the International Polar Year (IPY) Education and Outreach Assessment (2010 - 2011), the APECS Nordic Project “Bridging Early Career Researchers and Indigenous People in Nordic Countries” (2013 - 2015), the APECS-CliC Project “Where at they now” (2014-2016) as well as the APECS involvement in the EU Horizon2020-funded projects APPLICATE (Advanced Prediction in Polar regions and beyond: modelling, observing system design and Linkages associated with a Changing Arctic climaTE) (since 2016), and INTERACT (International Network for Terrestrial Research and Monitoring in the Arctic) (since 2016).

Thank you to the many volunteers and mentors that have helped us over the years! And thank you also to our many APECS members worldwide for participating in our events, providing us ideas for activities and helping us to shape the future of Polar research! We are looking forward to the next 10 years!

4. APECS Online Activities and Publications

4.1. APECS International Online Conference 2017

The third annual APECS Online Conference 2017 took place on **20 March 2017** from 07:30 to 00:30 GMT. This year's theme was "Outside the Box: encouraging alternative solutions for undertaking and communicating polar research." As a new generation of polar researchers stepping up to the plate, we must embrace new and innovative polar challenges. Our ability to successfully address such challenges and steer the polar world in a positive direction has far-reaching local, regional, and global consequences.

The conference attracted more people than ever before with over 40 presenters and 138 registered participants (105 attending). We had a full and successful day of presentations on *Outside the Box* polar research. The presenters covered a wide range of topics ranging from social to physical to life sciences, as well as educational and managerial talks.

Thank you to all presenters and audience members for making the day a huge success! More of us are now thinking "Outside the Box" to address polar challenges facing our generation. Special thanks to Jane Francis - Director of the British Antarctic Survey, and John Walsh - Chief Scientist at the International Arctic Research Center (IARC), for their inspiring keynote presentations that were very well received.

Prizes for the best presentations were awarded to:

- **Maciej Manko, Katarzyna Walczynska** received €200 for the **best Arctic presentation** titled: "On-board Citizen Science! How Tourist can Aid Marine Biodiversity Monitoring in Svalbard?" (session1)
- **Hernan Sala** received €200 for the best **Antarctic presentation** titled: "Why is it Hard to Communicate the Future of the Antarctic Ice Sheet?" (session 4)
- **Nuno Pereira** received €200 for the **most "Outside the Box" presentation** titled: "ViRAL: Virtual Reality Antarctica Laboratory" (session 2)

We congratulate our award winners and thank our sponsors, the **Association of Polar Early Career Scientists (APECS)** and the **Antarctic Science Ltd.** for funding the awards. We are also grateful to all the presenters and volunteers who made the conference possible.

Our conference theme was to venture "Outside the Box" for ideas that previous generations of polar researchers have left us, in order to overcome the severity of polar challenges we face. Striving to succeed, we must discover new ways of thinking and acting, using to our advantage: international and interagency collaborations; idea-sharing between poles; interdisciplinary and transdisciplinary approaches to research; technology and our ability to modify and develop it to suit our needs; affordable methods of research; improved ways of communicating scientific and social research; and most importantly ideas we haven't thought of yet but you have! To this end, this conference aimed to foster the sharing of alternative solutions for undertaking and communicating polar research, allowing a new generation of polar researchers to shine.

All sessions were recorded and are available on the APECS website:

Conference Session	Speaker	Registration # ¹	Attendee # ¹
Session 1 (07:30 - 09:50 GMT)	See list in the program .	54	40
Session 2 (10:45 - 12:15 GMT)	See list in the program .	57	38
Session 3 (13:30 - 15:45 GMT)	See list in the program .	47	28
Session 4 (16:45 - 19:00 GMT)	See list in the program .	39	21
Session 5 (19:45 - 21:45 GMT)	See list in the program .	34	23
Session 6 (22:30 - 00:30 GMT)	See list in the program .	33	13

4.2. APECS Webinars

APECS organized several webinars during the 2016-2017 term. These webinars were widely advertised via APECS communication channels and open to anyone. All webinars have also been added to the APECS Webinar archive on the APECS website.

Date	Title	Speaker	Registration # ¹	Attendee # ¹
Career Development Webinars				
25 Jan 2017	Expand Your Frontiers - APECS Career Path panel discussion for early career researchers	Dennis Fink, Katrin Bluhm, Lawrence Hislop, Bodil Bluhm		
16 Mar 2017	APECS Townhall Meetings Spring 2017 (2 sessions)	Multiple	50	30
7 Jun 2017	Making Antarctic Maps and Figures with Quantarctica	George Roth	111	62
21 Jun 2017	Arctic Data Center - Tools and Strategies for Archiving your Data	Amber Budden, Jesse Goldstein, Chris Jones	40	24
Alpine Cryosphere Webinar Series				
25 Apr 2017	Snow, ice, rivers and earthquakes - Himalayan Research and Life in Nepal	Joseph (Joe) Shea	58	34
24 May 2017	The first and only ice core histories from the Kilimanjaro ice fields	Dr. Lonnie G. Thompson	53	27
25 Sep 2017	Research Processes and Politics in the Peruvian Andes	Mark Carey	42	9
APECS Polar Week Webinars				
21 Mar 2017	APECS Polar Week Panel Discussion: Working in Collaboration with Communities and the Role of Traditional Knowledge	Multiple	34	19

23 Sep 2017	<u>APECS Polar Week Webinar: How to get involved: Insights from EPB, IASC and SCAR</u>	Joseph Nolan, Alevtina Evgrafova, Lavenia Ratnarajah, Jilda Caccavo	39	18
24 Sep 2017	<u>APECS-PEI Webinar: Kids are not your peer reviewer</u>	Julia Dooley	29	9
Other Webinars with Partners				
15 Mar 2017	<u>SCAR-COMNAP-APECS-Webinar: Writing for Success! Preparing winning fellowship applications - Spanish Version</u>	Multiple	95	48
19 Jul 2017	<u>YESS-APECS: The IPCC and Early Career Scientists Webinars (2 sessions)</u> In cooperation with the Young Earth System Scientists (YESS) Community	Multiple	226	126
28 Sep 2017	<u>Advanced Prediction in Polar Regions and Beyond</u>	Thomas Jung	42	23

¹ Minimum number of attendees. Several webinars connected to classrooms and / or meeting rooms where groups of participants shared one screen / log-in.

4.3. Social Media

APECS currently has 3829 “likes” on the APECS Facebook page as well as 3021 members in the APECS Facebook Group and 5551 followers on Twitter (@Polar_Research) plus additional ones on the various Social Media presences of the APECS National Committees (all numbers as of 24 September 2017):

Committee	Facebook (page)	Facebook (group)	Twitter	Instagram	VR
APECS Belgium	236	66	65		
APECS Brazil	1610				
APECS Bulgaria	822				
APECS Canada	574		552		
APECS Chile		258			
APECS Finland		67			
APECS France	459				
APECS Germany	74				
IPRN	1974				
APECS Italy	342				
APECS Japan	10				
APECS Netherlands	325		335		

APECS Oceania	430		511		
APECS Peru	44		8		
APECS Poland	146				
APECS Portugal	617		78	37	
Russian Polar Initiative	196		562	718	412
APECS Russia					724
APECS South Africa	93		30	81	
APECS Spain	309		234		
APECS Sweden		87	244		
APECS Turkey / Polar Research Centre	667		625	499	
UK Polar Network	727	727	2944	86	
USAPECS			229		

APECS Activity Highlights on Social Media during 2016-2017:

We try to make daily posts on all APECS social media channels, but particular highlights occur during the International Polar Weeks in March and September. We use social media to advertise events we are hosting during this time and also as an outreach tool. March Polar Week took place from March 20 - 26, 2017 with the theme of "People of the Poles". To honor the theme we had people use #PolarPeople on Twitter throughout the week to open up a dialogue between polar scientists, residents of the poles, and the public. We asked everyone to share short stories about their research or experience as polar scientists, what it's like to live in polar regions, and/or tell us what makes them #PolarPeople. We had really good engagement on Twitter using this hashtag throughout the week. We also used our Facebook page and Twitter during March Polar Week to showcase Polar Art, where we circulated 1 or 2 pieces of artwork of polar latitudes. Similarly, we advertised our Photo Contest by adding pictures to our social media accounts in advance of the submission deadline as examples for each category, which helped boost our submission numbers.

Join us on Saturday, September 23, starting at 12pm GMT / 8am EST, for the chance to ask polar scientists anything about our Polar World!

September Polar Week took place from September 18-24, 2017, with the theme of Polar World and International Collaboration. We had a similar twitter campaign although this time using #PolarWorld, which was slightly less successful than in March due to lack of advertising in advance. However, we hosted a #SciParty event on Twitter highlighting the Polar World theme which increased engagement. We used Facebook and Twitter to advertise the US APECS Polar Film Fest and APECS screenings of Glacial Balance. We also live tweeted during these events! Finally, we advertised our daily blog posts throughout the week which got a lot of attention as many people and NCs were involved in writing them so it was circulated widely.

We hosted a Reddit Ask Me Anything (AMA) during both Polar Weeks, which is a different form of social media. Both were quite successful, drawing questions from a large audience of non-scientists and showcasing what APECS does worldwide.

4.4. APECS Presentations and Publications

4.4.1. Presentations and Posters

In 2016-2017, many of our APECS members again presented about APECS and our projects at meetings and conferences around the world. Overview presentations about APECS were held among others at the APECS Balkan Meeting (October 2016), the APECS Netherlands / Belgium Symposium 2016, the APECS Oceania Symposium (2017), the Alfred Wegener Institute (Potsdam) (March 2017), the European Polar Board Meeting (April 2017), the Scientific Days of the Committee for French Research in the Arctic and the Antarctic (CNFRA) (May 2017), at universities in Peru, the relief voyage by the South African National Antarctic Program (SANAP) research vessel's (the SA Agulhas II) trip to Marion Island (of the Prince Edward Islands), the IAPSO-IAMAS-IAGA assembly in Cape Town, South Africa, in Chilean Antarctic Expedition (ECA53) in Escudero Chilean field station at King George Island and aboard the Aquiles ship, at the University of Dehli (India), and many more.

In addition, APECS presented some of its activities at conferences around the world as oral presentations or posters:

Title	Presenter(s) / Author(s)	Conference / Event / Meeting
Presentations		
The Association of Polar Early Career Scientists (APECS)	Gerlis Fugmann	Arctic Frontiers Seminar Abroad, Bremen, Germany, November 2016
APECS as a Stakeholder: Training Future Leadership within the Polar Research Community	Ruth Hindshaw, TJ Young, Alex Thornton, Hanne Nielsen, Josefine Lenz, Alice Bradley, Gerlis Fugmann,	The Future of Polar Governance: Knowledge, Laws, Regimes, and Resources, British Antarctic Survey, Cambridge, 27th March 2017

The Association of Polar Early Career Scientists (APECS)	Gerlis Fugmann	International Workshop of Polar Educators International 2017, Rovereto, Italy, April 2017
Arctic Science Outreach: Bridging Knowledge to Action (example of the Russian Arctic science outreach).	Yulia Zaika, Ekaterina Uryupova	International Conference on Arctic Science: Bringing Knowledge to Action, AMAP. Reston, USA. 2017
Digital Outreach with the Association of Polar Early Career Scientists	H. Nielsen, A. Thornton, & G. Fugmann, Christiansen, H.	SCAR Biology Symposium, Leuven, Belgium, July 2017
APECS - Future Directions	Jasmine Lee, Meagan Dewar, Gabriela Roldan	APECS Oceania Symposium, Melbourne, Australia, September 2017
Posters		
APECS as an Arctic Stakeholder: Training Future Leadership of the Polar Research Community	Alex Thornton, Josefine Lenz, Ruth Hindshaw, Gerlis Fugmann	ASSW 2017, March 2017
APECS' Online Conference, Virtual Posters, & Webinars to the World	Alex Thornton, Josefine Lenz, Alice Bradley, Gerlis Fugmann	ASSW 2017, March 2017
10 Years of APECS: Early Career Researchers and the Antarctic	Gabriela Roldan, Meagan Dewar, Jasmine Lee, Gerlis Fugmann	Theo Murphy "The Antarctic Frontier" conference, September 2017
10 Years of APECS: Fostering Antarctic Research in an International Context	Gabriela Roldan, Meagan Dewar, Jasmine Lee, Gerlis Fugmann	Communicating Across Borders Workshop, July 2017
Connecting, Popularising and Promoting Polar Science in India	IPRN	National Conference on Polar Sciences, 16-17 May, 2017, Goa, India.
<i>UKPN membership survey</i>	UKPN	poster at the Arctic Office Royal Society event, 18 Oct 2016, London
„APECS Germany“ Poster	APECS Germany	AWI Open Ship 2017 (RV Polarstern, Bremerhaven)
„APECS Germany“ Poster	APECS Germany	Science on the road 2017 (May and August 2017), several German cities
APECS an International Platform for Polar Research	Swati Nagar	India

4.4.2. Publications

Reports

Fugmann, G., Vingerhagen, R., Bradley, A. Mariash, H., Nielsen, H. and Vick-Majors, T. (2016): [APECS Annual Report 2015-2016](#). Tromso, Norway, 52p.

Fugmann, G., Fletcher T., Cooper, J., Schulze, V., Spolaor, A. and APECS Executive Committee 2016-2017 (2016): [Association of Polar Early Career Scientists \(APECS\) International Directorate Office - Shaping the Future of Polar Research \(Project: No. 229563\) - Final Results Report](#) for Research Council of Norway. Tromso, Norway, 46p.

Newsletters

Naito, A.T., Fugmann, G. and H. Midleja (eds.): APECS Newsletter. Published monthly.

- [October 2016](#)
- [November 2016](#)
- [January 2017](#)
- [February 2017](#)
- [March 2017](#)
- [April 2017](#)
- [May 2017](#)
- [June 2017](#)
- [July / August 2017](#)
- [September 2017](#)

APECS-Brazil

- APECS Brazil [Informative](#), Year VII, Edition II, July to December 2016
- APECS-Brazil [Informative](#) , Year VIII, Edition I, January to June 2017

APECS South Africa

- [APECS South Africa Newsletter 1](#), August 2017

Indian Polar Research Network (IPRN)

- [Polar Bytes](#) Vol 2, Issue 2, December 2016

Other Publications

Caramello, N. D. A., Assunção Ivar do Sul, J., Silva Souza, J., Alves dos Santos, E., da Cruz Piuco, R., Freiburger Affonso, S., Elias-Piera, F., Silva, M., da Costa Rodrigues, L.A., Xavier, J. and E. Schneider Costa (2017): [Ciência Polar e a Comunicação entre estudantes, educadores e cientistas \(engl.: Polar Science and Science Communication among students, educators and scientists\)](#). Rev. Elet. Cient. UERGS, , v. 3, n. 2, p.340-371.

APECS Chile

[Press note](#) of APECS Chile as a formal organization

3. Helping Members Interact

3.1. APECS events for early career researchers

APECS and its National Committees organise events (e.g. workshops, panel discussions, networking events) for ECRs regularly around the world. In the 2016-2017 term, it was a total of 38 reported events in 20 countries. A summary for most of the events can be found on the APECS website through the link provided in the table. We also highlight a few selected events below the table.

Figure 6: APECS events for early career researchers in 2016-2017

Event	Date	Location	(Co-)Organizer
Workshops and Meetings			
<u>UKPN Poster Workshop at the Challenger Conference for Marine Science</u>	5 - 8 Sep 2016	Liverpool, UK	UKPN
<u>APECS Germany Workshop on Proposal Writing</u>	14 Sep 2016	Rostock, Germany	APECS Germany
<u>Finnish-Japanese early career arctic scientists (ECASs) workshop</u>	17 Oct 2016	Helsinki, Finland	APECS Finland / APECS Japan
<u>APECS Balkan Workshop</u>	1 - 2 Oct 2016	Kardjali, Bulgaria	APECS Bulgaria / APECS Turkey / APECS Romania
<u>APECS Portugal Workshop 2016</u>	26 Oct 2016	Lisbon, Portugal	APECS Portugal
<u>APECS Netherlands / Belgium Symposium 2016</u>	2 Nov 2016	The Haag, Netherlands	APECS Netherlands / APECS Belgium
<u>APECS Sweden Workshop at PolarForum</u>	26 Nov 2016	Stockholm, Sweden	APECS Sweden
<u>Science communication workshop 'Improving Communication Effectiveness and Capacity Addition in Polar Science (ICECAPS) 2016</u>	1 - 2 Dec 2016	Dehradun, India	IPRN
<u>Workshop „Poster Design“ at the 9th annual meeting of the working group for permafrost</u>	9-11 Feb 2017	Einsiedeln, Switzerland	APECS Germany / APECS Switzerland / PYRN - DACH
<u>APECS Sweden Gothenburg Polar Pub</u>	21 Feb 2017	Gothenburg, Sweden	APECS Sweden
<u>UKPN-Challenger Early Career Workshop on Project Communication</u>	17 Mar 2017	Southampton, UK	UKPN
<u>APECS Online Townhall Meetings</u>	16 Mar 2017	Online	APECS

<u>APECS International Online Conference 2017: Outside the Box</u>	20 Mar 2017	Online	APECS
Papanin readings	28 Mar 2017	Arhangelsk, Russia	Polar Initiative (Russia)
<u>APECS Workshop at ASSW 2017</u>	2 Apr 2017	Prague, Czech Republic	APECS
APECS Executive Committee in-person meeting at ASSW 2017	3-4 Apr 2017	Prague, Czech Republic	APECS
<u>Early-Career Workshop "Inter-disciplinary cooperation and multi-stakeholder cooperation through the notion of 'boundary objects'" at ASSW 2017</u>	6 Apr 2017	Prague, Czech Republic	APECS / IASC / ASSW
<u>APECS-IASC-AMAP Workshop on "Scientific Assessments: Process, Dissemination and Impact" at International Conference on Arctic Science: Bringing Knowledge to Action</u>	24 Apr 2017	Reston, Virginia, USA	APECS / IASC / AMAP
APECS Switzerland Workshop	11 May 2017	Bern, Switzerland	APECS Switzerland
<u>APECS France at Scientific Days of CNFRA (including APECS France communication workshop)</u>	11 - 12 May 2017	Paris, France	APECS France
APECS Japan Workshop at Japan Geoscience Union meeting 2017	24 May 2017	Chiba, Japan	APECS Japan
<u>UKPN-Challenger Early Career Workshop on Project Management, Outreach and Polar Science</u>	15 June 2017	Cambridge, UK	UKPN
<u>APECS Workshop: "Communicating Across Borders"</u>	4 Jul 2017	Hobart, Australia	APECS Oceania
<u>APECS workshop at SCAR Biology Symposium 2017</u>	9 Jul 2017	Leuven, Belgium	APECS / APECS Belgium
<u>Swiss Polar Day</u>	7 Sep 2017	Zürich, Switzerland	APECS Switzerland
<u>Polar Science Communication Workshop</u>	12-14 Aug 2017	Boulder, USA	USAPECS
<u>Social Media and Science Communication workshop at the SCAR PAIS Conference</u>	11 Sep 2017	Trieste, Italy	APECS Italy
<u>APECS Oceania Symposium</u>	18 - 19 Sep 2017	Melbourne, Australia	APECS Oceania
<u>APECS Germany Workshop 2017</u>	20 Sep 2017	Erlangen, Germany	APECS Germany
Two workshops/talks about APECS activities and content for national young professionals.	No date reported	Peru	APECS Peru

<u>APECS Italy Workshop on Social Media and Science Communication</u>	11 Sept. 2017	Trieste, Italy	APECS Italy
<u>APECS Italy Workshop: Climate, humans and the environment: a lengthy history</u>	29 Sept 2017	Venice, Italy	APECS Italy
Panels			
<u>APECS Sweden Career Panel at Forum for Research into Ice Shelf Processes (FRISP)</u>	2 Oct 2016	Kristineberg, Sweden	APECS Sweden
<u>APECS Panel on Balancing work and personal life during the IGS Nordic Branch Meeting</u>	27 Oct 2016	Tromsø, Norway	APECS
<u>APECS-AGU Cryosphere Lunchtime Careers Panel</u>	14 Dec 2016	San Francisco, USA	USAPECS
<u>Panel discussion: Shape the future of polar geosciences</u>	28 Jan 2017	Delhi, India	IPRN
<u>APECS Career Path panel</u> at Arctic Frontiers	25 Jan 2017	Tromsø, Norway	APECS / Arctic Frontiers Young
<u>APECS-EGU Cryosphere Polar Science Career Panel</u>	27 Apr 2017	Vienna, Austria	APECS Germany, Bulgaria and Austria/ EGU Cryospheric ECS / EGU
<u>APECS Panel at ICASS IX</u>	5 Jun 2017	Umea, Sweden	APECS
<u>UKPN Career Panel on “International Collaboration”</u>	20 Sep 2017	Oban, United Kingdom	UKPN

3.1.1. International Event Highlights

APECS Workshop at ASSW 2017 2 April 2017, Prague, Czech Republic

On Sunday 2 April around 50 ECRs assembled in the Clarion Congress Hotel Prague for a one-day workshop organised by APECS prior to the start of Arctic Science Summit Week. The day started with two panel discussions and after lunch, participants could attend two of three different breakout sessions. By the end of the day we had all learnt something new (did you know that there are flamingos in Siberia?!) and came away with new ideas and friends. Read more what happened that day on the [APECS website](#). APECS in cooperation with the International Arctic Science Committee (IASC) also organised the poster awards for the ECRs attending the conference. We would like to thank all the judges who contributed their time to judge the posters and of course to all the presenters! Find out more about who the winners were in chapter 6 and on the [APECS website](#).

APECS-IASC-AMAP Workshop: Scientific Assessments: Process, Dissemination and Impact
24 April 2017, Reston, Virginia, United States

APECS in cooperation with the International Arctic Science Committee (IASC) and the Arctic Monitoring and Assessment Programme (AMAP) organised a workshop on “Scientific Assessments: Process, Dissemination and Impact” at the 2017 International Conference on Arctic Science: Bridging Knowledge to Action in Reston, Virginia, United States on 24 April 2017. This one-day workshop engaged researchers in a conversation on scientific assessments with an international group of scientists and communication experts in government and academia through interactive panels and presentations. Workshop outcomes also contributed to a discussion during plenary sessions on a call for action held on the last day of the conference. Contributions from the workshop echoed major themes that emerged throughout the conference, with usability of scientific assessment for policy and decision support being most prominent. Read the article on the [APECS website](#).

APECS Workshop at the SCAR Biology Symposium 2017
9 July 2017, Leuven, Belgium

One day ahead of the recent 2017 SCAR Biology Symposium, APECS organised an ECR workshop for conference participants (and anyone else interested). For this workshop, 37 people (+4 speakers) met already on Sunday morning on KU Leuven premises. The main workshop theme was “communicating with a non-scientific audience”.

After getting organised, we jumped right in with José Xavier, scientist in Portugal and England, explaining what science communication is and why it is important. Siska Waelkens, working for the Faculty of Science of KU Leuven, then talked about the bridge that scientists need to build between themselves and others to facilitate mutual understanding. We continued with a coffee break (also very important for communication...). Stéphanie Brabant from France TV subsequently showed footage recorded during the recent Antarctic Circumnavigation Expedition. She showed both good and less good examples of live interviews, outlining aspects that are critical to keep in mind when being interviewed as a scientist. Lastly, we switched topics with Grant Humphries (from <http://blackbawks.net/>) up next, talking about scientific data management – another crucial issue for basically any scientist. Read more about workshop on the APECS website.

3.1.2. Highlights in our main APECS International Directorate Host Countries

3.1.2.1. Germany

1st APECS Germany Workshop

14 September 2016, Rostock, Germany

APECS Germany, which recently formed in July 2016, held its first workshop in Rostock, Germany on 14 September 2016. Prior to the annual coordination workshop by the German Priority Research Program on Antarctic research, 19 participants joined the ECR workshop - most of whom were new to APECS. They benefited from five mentors in polar research giving their secrets on how to increase chances for their proposals to be a success. During the panel discussion, **Sonja Berg** (University of Cologne), **Mirko Scheinert** (Technische Universität Dresden), **Inna Sokolova** (University of Rostock), **Charlotte Havermans** (University of Bremen) and **Florian Leese** (University of Duisburg-Essen) answered questions on how to receive feedback, how to approach colleagues, or simply advised to celebrate a success when it happens! Link to the report on the APECS website.

2nd APECS Germany Workshop

20 September 2017, Erlangen, Germany

In the run-up of the coordination workshop of the priority programme 'Antarctic Research with comparative investigations in Arctic ice areas' (SPP 1158), APECS Germany organized a panel discussion on career paths and funding opportunities for postdocs. After an introduction to APECS, two invited speakers gave an impulse presentation from different perspective: Prof. Ben Fabry (Professor for Medical Physics and Technology at FAU Erlangen-Nuremberg) and Dr. Rainer Lehmann (teacher at the Freie Waldorfschule Hannover-Bothfeld, working group "polar teacher") gave insights about their professional careers to the 15 PhD students who participated. Afterwards, plenty of questions were asked and a lively discussion on strategies for career development inside and outside academia and the current situation in Germany developed. In the course of the general SPP workshop, an oral presentation on APECS, recent activities of the network and highlights of APECS Germany were given by Board members Tim Carlsen and Stefanie Arndt. A workshop report can be found on the APECS Germany website. Read about the workshop on the [APECS Germany website](#).

3.1.2.2. Norway

APECS Panel - Balancing work and personal lives

27 October 2016, Tromsø, Norway

During the IGS Nordic Branch Meeting in Tromsø on the 27th of October 2016, APECS Council member Vikram Goel organised an APECS Panel on Balancing work and personal life. It was an open discussion with questions and comments from the attending audience. The event was organised during the lunch break on the second day of the meeting. The panelists included Dr. Alun Hubbard, Dr. Miriam Jackson, Dr. Ioanna Merkerandi. Read the report on the APECS website.

APECS panel - Which career path would you like to follow?

25 January 2017, Tromsø, Norway

During the [Arctic Frontiers 2017 Conference](#) in Tromsø Norway, APECS organised a panel discussion on 25 January (Which career path would you like to follow?) about different career paths in Arctic science, inside and outside academia. The panelists represented various career possibilities: Bodil Bluhm is a professor at [UiT The Arctic University of Norway](#); Katrin Bluhm works as a coordinator of the science part of Arctic Frontiers at [Akvaplan-niva](#); Lawrence Hislop works with science management in [Climate and Cryosphere project \(CliC\)](#); and Dennis Fink facilitates science communication through his company [Mediomix](#). Following introductions, the audience posed questions, and the experiences, choices, and random encounters that led to these positions were discussed. Read the report on the [APECS website](#).

3.2. Education and Outreach Events

Education and Outreach is one of the main focus areas of APECS. During 2016-2017, APECS and its National Committees again organized many events dedicated to the public around the world. In addition, APECS organized two International Polar Weeks in March 2017 and September 2017 as well as participated with several partners in Antarctica Day, providing an opportunity for focused education and outreach activities around the world during these times:

Figure 7: APECS Education and Outreach Events during 2016-2017

3.2.1. Antarctica Day 2016

APECS and several of its national Committees participated again in Antarctic Day 2016 on 1 December 2016. A project group within the APECS Council helped to coordinate activities on the international side this year. Members

of the project group were: T.J. Young, Swati Nagar, Jilda Caccavo. In addition, several of the APECS National Committees and other APECS members have again contributed with events around the world. We want to thank everyone involved!!

Event	Date	Location	(Co-)Organizer
Many events were organized worldwide. For a full list, go see the Antarctica Day 2016 Event List . Below are some highlights of activities reported specifically from APECS National Committees:			
Lunch-Seminar / Picture-show at AWI Potsdam	1 Dec 2016	Potsdam, Germany	APECS Germany
Antarctic Photo Competition		Online	APECS Belgium
APECS Switzerland event	1 - 2 Dec 2016	Zurich, Switzerland	APECS Switzerland
APECS Italy Antarctica Day 2016 Seminar	1 Dec 2016	Venice, Italy	APECS Italy / Ca' Foscari University of Venice
Science communication workshop 'Improving Communication Effectiveness and Capacity Addition in Polar Science (ICECAPS) 2016	1 - 2 Dec 2016	Dehradun, India	IPRN
Antarctica Day Flag Event	1 Dec 2016		UKPN

3.2.2. APECS International Polar Weeks

APECS organized again two successful International Polar Weeks in the 2016-2017 term. A project group within the APECS Council helped to coordinate the activities on the international side this year. Members of the project group were: Jose Seco, Sara Strey, Liz Ceperley, Swati Nagar and Jean Holloway. In addition, many of the APECS National Committees and other APECS members have again contributed with events around the world. We want to thank everyone involved!!

3.2.2.1. APECS International Polar Week March 2017

For the **APECS International Polar Week March 2017** from **20 - 27 March 2017**, the overall theme was **"People of the Poles: Human Use and Appreciation of Earth's Polar Regions"**. We wanted to showcase all the #PolarPeople who live, work, vacation, or are connected to the poles. Events we hosted include: "Polar Science 101: Breaking Down Scientific Concepts For a General Audience" blog series; online Polar Art Showcase; "Working in Collaboration with Indigenous People and the Role of Traditional Knowledge in Northern Research" online panel discussion; Reddit AMA; #PolarPeople Photo Contest; #PolarPeople Twitter campaign.

Event	Date	Location	(Co-) Organizer
For a full list of events go to the Polar Week page. Below are the events reported by APECS and its National Committees			
<u>APECS International Polar Week Photo Contest 2017</u>	All week	Online	APECS
<u>Virtual Polar Art Exhibition</u>	All week	Online	APECS
<u>Polar Science 101 Blogs:</u> Breaking down scientific concepts for a general audience	All week	Online	APECS
<u>Polar Week Twitter Campaign:</u> #PolarPeople	20 - 26 Mar 2017	Online / Twitter	APECS
<u>Polar Week Reddit Science AMA</u> ("Ask Me Anything")	25 Mar 2017	Online	UKPN
<u>APECS Polar Week Panel Discussion:</u> Working in Collaboration with Indigenous People and the Role of Traditional Knowledge in Northern Research. Link to recording	21 Mar 2017	Online	APECS
<u>Talk: What lies beneath the ice? - Role of Geologists in Antarctic Sciences</u>	24 Mar 2017	Delhi, India	IPRN
La Salle Esteio Secondary School, Esteio, RS: students make their own Antarctic flags (total of 60) in the Antarctic Day, 2016 (coordinated by Roberta Piuco). Claudineia Lizieri (also APECS-Brazil council member) also gave a lecture during the IPW.	No date reported	Brazil	APECS Brazil
Workshop "REGIÕES POLARES NO ENSINO DE CIÊNCIAS: UMA ABORDAGEM GLOBALIZADA COM RECURSOS LÚDICOS", Curitiba, PR, for elementary school teachers from municipal schools.	No date reported	Brazil	APECS Brazil

Lecture about researcher activities in Antarctica at Duque Estrada Municipal School	No date reported	São Gonçalo, Brazil	APECS Brazil
"Trazendo a Antártica para o UniBH"! The IPW in Belo Horizonte, MG coordinated by Claudineia Lizieri (APECS-Brazil council member).	No date reported	Brazil	APECS Brazil
Instituto Ivoti, Ivoti - RS: Júlia Finger (APECS collaborator) gave a lecture on her Antarctic research to students from several schools. Also, Ailim Schwambach (APECS-Brazil council member) organized an exposition with Antarctic photographs.	No date reported	Brazil	APECS Brazil
Capital do Saber School, Feliz, RS: students make their own Antarctic flags in the Antarctic Day, 2016. Flags were sent to Antarctica through the Brazilian Navy and Our Spaces initiative.	No date reported	Brazil	APECS Brazil

APECS Polar Week March 2017 Highlights

Blog: Polar Science 101: Breaking down scientific concepts for a general audience

Understanding science is important for everyone, whether it is used for evidence-based decision-making, managing industrial companies, for employment, in voting as private citizens, or in making decisions about your home and family. Science communication is an important part of conducting research, especially in polar regions where access to in situ information is challenging for the public to obtain. The goal of this blog

series is to break down some important topics in polar research so that a general audience can understand the key concepts.

The APECS Polar Week team contributed six posts over the week:

- [Future of the Cryosphere: Melting Glaciers and Thawing Permafrost](#) (Author: Jean Holloway)
- [Polar Contaminants](#) (Author: Jose Seco)
- [Antarctic Lakes - Nature's Laboratory](#) (Author: Swati Nagar)
- [The frozen history of the Earth - Reconstructing the past climate through ice cores](#) (Author: Francois Burgay)
- [The Past is the Key to the Present: Constraining Past Glacier Movements Using Surface Exposure Dating](#) (Author: Elizabeth Ceperley)
- [Arctic Climate Change and Midlatitude Weather - Why You Should Care about What's Going on up There](#) (Author: Sara Strey)

Virtual Polar Art Exhibition

For the first time, APECS organized a Virtual Polar Art Exhibition during the International Polar Week Spring 2017. In total, 11 artists participated in the event displaying their polar-inspired artwork which can be seen on the [APECS website](#).

We want to thank the artists Cory Trépanier, Lyn Kirkland, Les White, Linda Skoglund, Abraham Anghik Ruben, Allyson Comstock, Helene Girard, Vincent Reed, Xavier Cortada, Marina Rees, Koen Lybaert for their contributions!

APECS Fieldwork Photo Competition 2017

During the APECS International Polar Week Spring 2017, APECS organized a [fieldwork photo competition](#), where APECS members were encouraged to submit photos within 3 categories and later vote for the prettiest, funniest, most interesting photo for each category. Overall we received 60 photos and after the voting the following 3 winners received a prize:

1st Prize in the "PolarPeople & wildlife" category: **Gabriela Roldan** (Gateway Antarctica, University of Canterbury, New Zealand)

1st Prize in the "PolarPeople in action" category: **Stefano Ambroso** (Institut de ciencias del mar (CSIC), Spain)

1st Prize in the "PolarPeople at home" category: **Elizabeth Erickson** (University of California, Santa Barbara, United States)

3.2.2.1. APECS International Polar Week September 2017

Our goal for the **APECS International Polar Week September 2017** from **18 - 24 September 2017**, was to have more involvement from different APECS National Committees. With this in mind, we wanted to have an international theme, showcasing different kinds of international collaboration. We wanted to specifically highlight how we are living in a **#PolarWorld**, where issues happening in the poles affect everyone on the globe. Events include the Frostbytes Competition, blog series, #PolarWorld and SciParty on Twitter, Reddit AMA. We also helped with US APECS' #PolarFilmFest screening of "Glacial Balance" (documentary) by nine National Committees in ten international locations.

Event	Date	Location	Organizer
For a full list of events go to the Polar Week page . Below are the events reported by APECS and its National Committees			
IPRN's "Poles to Schools" program	No date reported	Dehradun / Delhi, India	IPRN
APECS Oceania Symposium	18 - 19 Sep 2017	Melbourne, Australia	APECS Oceania
APECS Sweden Stockholm Polar Pub	20 Sep 2017	Stockholm, Sweden	APECS Sweden
APECS Sweden GBG Polar mini Conference	20 Sep 2017	Gothenburg, Sweden	APECS Sweden
2nd Polar Film Fest	entire week	Several locations	USAPECS
Polar Week Watch Party of USAPECS Polar Film Fest	entire week	several northern locations including Whitehorse, Canada	APECS Canada
French Polar Week at Nausicaa	3 - 6 Oct 2017	Boulogne sur Mer, France	APECS France
Polar Week Reddit AMA	23 Sep 2017	Online	APECS
APECS Polar Week Coffee Break	20 Sep 2017	Fairbanks, Alaska, USA	
<u>UKPN Career Panel on "International Collaboration"</u>	20 Sep 2017	Oban, UK	UKPN
Lunchtime Lectures: South Africa at the Poles	19 Sep 2017	Bloemfontein, South Africa	APECS South Africa
DOCU-FILM "RESET a class at the Svalbard"	26 Oct 2017	Milan, Italy	APECS Italy
Polar Week Celebration 2017	21 Sep 2017	Goa, India	IPRN
Glacial Balances screenings for Polar Film Fest	All week	Buenos Aires (Argentina), Ottawa (Canada), Santiago (Chile), Paris (France), Potsdam (Germany), Vasco (India), Moscow (Russia), Bloemfontein (South Africa), Boulder, Colorado (USA), Fairbanks (USA)	USAPECS
APECS Germany Workshop: Career paths and funding opportunities for postdocs	20 Sep 2017	Erlangen, Germany	APECS Germany
APECS Bulgaria Open Conference	22 Sep 2017	Sinemorets, Bulgaria	APECS Bulgaria

IRPN Presentation about "Arctic polar world and Arctic science"

22 Sep 2017

Delhi, India

IPRN

APECS International Polar Week September 2017 Highlights

US Polar Film Festival and "Glacial Balance" Screening

GLACIAL BALANCE
A DOCUMENTARY
www.GlacialBalance.com

10 free, public APECS screenings
in 9 countries on 5 continents for
International Polar Week!

Buenos Aires, Argentina*
Fri., 22 Sept. | 3:00pm

Ottawa, Canada*
Tues., 19 Sept. | 8:00pm

Santiago, Chile
Wed., 20 Sept. | 6:00pm

Paris, France
Thurs., 21 Sept. | 8:00pm

Potsdam, Germany
Thurs., 21 Sept. | 6:00pm

Vasco, India*
Thurs., 21 Sept. | 2:00pm

Moscow, Russia*
Mon., 18 Sept. | 4:15pm

Bloemfontein, South Africa*
Wed., 20 Sept. | 6:30pm

Boulder, Colorado, USA
Tues., 19 Sept. | 6:00pm

Fairbanks, Alaska, USA*
Fri., 22 Sept. | 6:00pm

* = Screening also features a Q&A session with polar scientists!

For more details on these #PolarWeek events, visit:
<http://usapecs.wixsite.com/usapecs/glacial-balance-screenings>

The Association of Polar Early Career Scientists (APECS) & Dalton Films are proud to screen *Glacial Balance* at free, public events for US APECS' 2nd International Polar Film Fest!

POLAR Film Fest
18-22 September 2017

In conjunction with Polar Week 2017, USAPECS is announcing the second annual

Suggest or submit films for any of the following categories, in any language, by 25 August at tinyurl.com/y9vw8gn8

MONDAY
#POLARWORLD

TUESDAY
SCIENCE IN ACTION

WEDNESDAY
PEOPLE AT THE POLES

THURSDAY
POLAR POLICY

FRIDAY
ICING ON THE CAKE

Find out more at usapecs.wixsite.com/usapecs/pff2017

More information available on the [USAPECS website](http://usapecs.wixsite.com/usapecs).

#PolarWorld Polar Week Blog

APECS released a series of blog posts during Polar Week to promote #PolarWorld and polar research in general. The blogs discussed the key issues happening in the poles that are affecting the globe, talk about international collaborations and conducting research internationally, and help raise awareness about some of the international activities APECS is part of. Many thanks to the authors of the blogs for contributing to this series, including many APECS National Committees.

Topics:

- [Polar Issues are Global Issues](#) (Author: Jean Holloway)
- [Scientists All Over the World](#) (Author: Jean Holloway)
- [People of the Poles – Perspectives from APECS Canada](#) (Authors: Meagan Grabowski, Jen Sidorova, Marianne Falardeau-Coté, Jean Holloway)
- [International Polar Organizations: Connecting the #PolarWorld](#) (Author: Joseph Nolan, EPB)
- [Friday Fun - Research Stories](#) (Authors: Jose Seco, Marianna Pinzone, Nicole Hellessey, Helena Baird, Alison Webb, Terri Souster)

- [How You Can Get Involved](#) (Authors: Jose Seco, Sara Strey, Tom Armitage, Jilda Caccavo, Joseph Nolan, Lavenia Ratnarajah)
- [E&O, polar explorations and women in science: The 1st Homeward Bound Expedition](#) (Author: Betty Trummel - PEI)

3.2.3. Other Outreach Events

APECS and its National Committees also organize many other Outreach events during the year that do not fall within our Polar Weeks and Antarctica Day. Here are some of the highlights from 2016 - 2017.

Event	Date	Location	(Co-)Organizer
UKPN at the Making in Transit Seminar Series	8 Dec 2016	UK	UKPN
APECS Canada at the Haines Junction Mountain Festival	9 - 11 Dec 2016	Canada	APECS Canada
Arctic Frontiers Science for Schools	24 / 26 Jan 2017	Tromsø, Norway	APECS / Science Centre of Northern Norway / Arctic Frontiers
Arctic Frontiers Science for Politics	25 Jan 2017	Tromsø, Norway	APECS / Science Centre of Northern Norway / Arctic Frontiers
Workshop for school students at Leeds Science Festival	Mar 2017	Leeds, UK	UKPN
IPRN Talk “What lies beneath the ice - Role of Geologists in Antarctic Sciences”	24 Mar 2017	India	IPRN
“Polarforschung zum Anfassen“ (engl. “Polar science you can touch”) at the long night of science	24 June 2017	Potsdam, Germany	APECS Germany
Lecture about polar expeditions for young geographers	4 July 2017	Russia	Polar Initiative (Russia)
IPRN talk about 'How stations work in Antarctica and How is Antarctic wintering'	25 Aug 2017	India	IPRN
Bristol Event: “Meet the Expert: Polar Scientists”	No date reported	Bristol, UK	UKPN and @Bristol Science Centre
4. Exposition "Brazil in Antarctica and Blue Amazon" during the 31 st Mostratec conference in Novo Hamburgo, RS.	No date reported	Brazil	APECS Brazil

Other Outreach Events - Highlights

Arctic Frontiers Science for Schools

January 2017

Tromsø, Norway

During the annual Arctic Frontiers 2017 conference in Tromsø (Norway), APECS and the Nordnorsk Vitensenter Tromsø (Science Centre of Northern Norway) organized a unique event for schools to learn about Arctic science. Over the course of three days, 13-18 year old students from a number of schools attended diverse presentations by early career scientists from all over the world.

Read more on the [APECS website](#).

Arctic Frontiers Science for Politics

January 2017

Tromsø, Norway

Two of the early career researchers, Megan O'Sadnick (Research Scientist at Norut Narvik) and Mar Fernández-Méndez (Postdoctoral researcher at the Norwegian Polar Institute) had the opportunity during the Arctic Frontiers 2017 Science for Politics event, organized by the Science Centre of Northern Norway (Nordnorsk Vitensenter Tromsø) in cooperation with Arctic Frontiers and APECS to speak with students from Tromsø who are interested in becoming politicians about the interaction between science and politics.

Read more on the [APECS website](#).

APECS Germany at the Long Night of Science at AWI Potsdam

June 2017

Potsdam, Germany

Every year in summer, universities and research institutions in Berlin and Potsdam open their doors to the public to give insights by giving presentations, show experiments and invite people to hands-on activities. At AWI Potsdam, APECS Germany members presented an APECS poster and were involved in several activities: Kids could try on polar clothes in a real field camp, filter water samples and touch a huge ice block while observing with a thermal camera how the surface temperature changes. Permafrost was featured as a special topic. In the course of the warm summer night, the effects of permafrost thaw was simulated with sand and ice cubes in wooden boxes. Kids were digging for fossils, tools and sensors with a metal detector in a big "permafrost" sand box while real bones and poster informed about actual findings in permafrost research. Read the report on the [APECS Germany website](#).

5. APECS Project Highlights

5.1. APPLICATE and INTERACT

UiT The Arctic University of Norway and its Faculty of Biosciences Fisheries and Economics in cooperation with the Association of Polar Early Career Scientists (APECS) are partners in the two

EU Horizon2020-funded projects APPLICATE (Advanced Prediction in Polar regions and beyond: Modelling, observing system design and Linkages associated with Arctic Climate change) and INTERACT (International Network for Terrestrial Research and Monitoring in the Arctic).

Co-funded by the Horizon 2020 programme of the European Union

APPLICATE is an EU HORIZON 2020 Research and Innovation Programme-financed project involving 16 partners from nine countries (Belgium, France, Germany, Iceland, Norway, Russia, Spain, Sweden and the United Kingdom). The multinational and multidisciplinary consortium will work to enhance weather and climate prediction capabilities not only in the Arctic, but also in Europe, Asia, and North America. The ability to develop adequate tools to predict when and how severe weather systems will affect Europe, Asia and North America is vital to the inhabitant of these regions. For more information visit the [APPLICATE website](http://www.apPLICATE.eu).

INTERACT is an EU HORIZON 2020 funded infrastructure project under the auspices of SCANNET, a circumarctic network of currently 83 terrestrial field bases in northern Europe, Russia, US, Canada, Greenland, Iceland, the Faroe Islands and Scotland, as well as stations in northern alpine areas. INTERACT specifically seeks to build capacity for research and monitoring in the European Arctic and beyond, and is offering access to numerous research stations through the [Transnational Access program](#). For more information visit the [INTERACT website](#).

Co-funded by the Horizon 2020 programme of the European Union

Over the four-year duration of the projects, the UiT / APECS tasks within the APPLICATE and INTERACT projects are focused primarily on training and outreach activities that complement APECS activities. The tasks will include, but are not limited to, organizing a Summer School, the development of an Online Course, and other online training resources for APPLICATE, as well as developing a fieldwork planning handbook and a practical field guide for INTERACT.

In the 2016-2017 term, APECS has hired a project officer to manage the UiT / APECS tasks in both projects and also assist with other APECS activities as needed. [Dr. Fiona Tummon](#), who started her work on 1 October 2017, is based at UiT The Arctic University of Norway and is part of the distributed APECS International Directorate Office.

The first project activities that started during the 2016-2017 term are:

- Planning for the [Polar Prediction School 2018](#) which will be from 17 - 27 April 2018 at Abisko Scientific Research Station in Sweden. The field school is a cooperation between APPLICATE project, APECS, UiT as well as the World Meteorological Organisation's Polar Prediction Project (PPP) in occasion of the Year of Polar Prediction (YOPP) and other partners.
- The first webinar of a short series of webinars related to the APPLICATE project was held on 28 September 2017, with the APPLICATE project lead Prof. Dr. Thomas Jung introducing the project in a presentation called ["Advanced Prediction in Polar Regions and Beyond"](#).

The APECS Executive Director Dr. Gerlis Fugmann also attended the kick-off meetings of the two projects in Reykjavik, Iceland (INTERACT) in January 2017 and Bremerhaven (APPLICATE) in February 2017.

5.2. APECS Council Projects

The APECS Council 2016-2017 had several project groups with which members could get involved. Some of them were related to planning APECS events such as workshops and panels (see chapter 3.1.) or the APECS International Polar Weeks (see chapter 3.2.2.) and Antarctica Day 2016 (see chapter 3.2.1.). Here we only list those projects not previously covered in other chapters of this report. All of these projects are continuing in the 2017-2018 term and so will even further increase their activities and resources:

5.2.1. Alpine Cryosphere Project Group

Goal: To increase the amount of resources APECS has with regards to the Alpine Cryosphere in non-polar regions.

Summary: Within the 2016-2017 term, the group focused on organising three webinars (**see chapter 4.2.**) in spring and fall 2017 on Alpine-Cryosphere related issues in non-polar regions. The group has also started to compile Alpine Cryosphere-related graduate programs to be added to the [APECS Graduate Programmes Database](#).

Group Members: Merran Smith (Chair), Alice Bradley, Kabir Rasouli, Alfonso Fernandez, Floreana Marie, Miesen and Jorgen Rosvold.

5.2.2. Non-Academic Careers Information (NACI)

Goals:

- Define 'non-academic', prioritize a set number of NAC types to focus on initially
- Provide information about NAC in the form of:
 - Webinars: Compile a list of existing webinars, both from APECS and outside
 - Creating a NAC portion of the APECS website, listed under 'career resources' including:
 - Profiles of individuals in NAC including interviews/bios/Q&A's
 - Useful links
 - Information about fellowships in NAC
 - Live Q&A sessions with individuals in NAC
 - Arrange a NAC workshop

Summary: In the 2016-2017 term, the group created the NAC portion of the APECS website and gathered content to showcase therein. They researched and reviewed existing webinars on NAC from both the APECS archive and generally, and links to these webinars, as well as brief descriptions, were compiled for the website. In addition, they created a list of interview questions for individuals in NAC, and proceeded to use those questions to interview several people currently in NAC. These interview questions and responses, as well as photos and short bios, were listed on the NAC website. They also started to compile book reviews, a list of useful websites/articles with more information about NAC as well as fellowship programs for ECR to become involved in NAC, and provided links to these on the NAC website. In the upcoming term 2017-2018, the group is planning to further expand its list of resources

Group Members: Jilda Caccavo (Chair), Vicki Sahanatien, Hanna Kauko, Friederike Gehrman, Adrian Dahood, Jilda Alicia Caccavo, Caroline Coch, Olivia Lee, Karolina Paquin

5.2.3. Summary of Polar Organizations

Goals:

- to provide information on Polar organisations in an approachable way
- To understand better and have better visuals of the universe of Polar Organisations
- To convey information better to those who are new to Polar research
- Good resource to have and to offer to the wider Polar community

Summary: During the 2016-2017 term, the group first set its goals and identified the challenges we faced with the large number of Polar organisations that are active today. Since the number of Polar organisations was very big, we decided to work first with the organisations that are official partners and sponsors of APECS and created a spreadsheet with this data. We investigated different ways to create a visual representation of the selected Polar Organisations, such as mind maps, bubble diagrams, chart, grid, etc. To look into who is the audience and what they would like to know, we ran a survey among the Council, and this is the summary of the results:

- more than 80% of the participants to the survey would like to know what is the focus subject and what opportunities are available within the Polar organisations
- 55% are familiar with the Polar organisations in their field
- more than 60% have not used the 'Who is who'/ acronyms table already available on the APECS website.

So we think the work of the group is a valuable contribution to APECS members and the Polar community in general. The group has started to work on a Prezi presentation with APECS partner and sponsors information as an example of data visualization which will be finalized in the coming term.

Group Members: Gabriela Roldan (Chair), Tamara Fletcher, Lorna Thurston, Laura Hobbs, Bruno Ibanez, Olivia Lee, Alice Bradley

5.3. APECS International Mentorship Award 2017

The 2017 APECS International Mentorship Award recipients were Dr. Hugues Lantuit and Dr. Renuka Badhe. These awards were established as a meaningful way to recognize and honor the efforts of mentors within the international polar science community who have devoted significant time and energy towards building a supportive community for early career researchers (ECRs).

We received several deserving nominations for both categories and it was difficult for our award committee to select the winners in both award categories:

Dr. Hugues Lantuit (Alfred Wegener Institute, Germany) is the 2017 recipient in the “APECS category”, where APECS committees were encouraged to nominate a mentor who has made an outstanding contribution to the success of APECS. Ten years ago, Hugues was the co-founder of APECS, a network that supported since its formation over 7600 members during the early stages of their careers. With this, as well as with the foundation of the Permafrost Young Researchers Network (PYRN), he “provided ECRs with platforms to get connected with each other and to get deeply involved into the international polar research landscape”.

Hugues has been an inspiration and bright example of passion for the polar sciences for many early career researchers and he provided solid foundations for future polar scientists to get actively engaged. Among others, through this position as the Executive Director of the International Permafrost Association (IPA) he helped to develop and maintain frameworks for the inclusion of ECRs at professional events, meetings, committees and working groups of which many APECS members have benefitted from over the years.

Hugues has been a great motivator and supporter for early career scientists. Since the foundation of APECS, he has been involved in many of our workshops and webinars, serving as a mentor for the participants and sharing his experience and advice; for example, how to navigate the world of polar acronyms or networking at conferences. Aided by his understanding that people will achieve more as a group than as individuals, he has supervised more than 20 PhD, Master’s, and Bachelor students. Nominators reiterated that “it was [Hugues] who infected [them] with the desire to learn more about the Polar regions” and provided the opportunity to succeed through fieldwork, speaking opportunities, and trusting them to take control of their academic careers.

Dr. Renuka Badhe (European Polar Board, Netherlands) is the 2017 recipient in the “member category”, where we encouraged APECS members to nominate someone who has been an outstanding personal mentor to them in their career. Dr. Badhe was nominated by several individuals who said that, “as far as mentors go, Renuka belongs in the ‘rockstar’ category.” Renuka has been a strong supporter of several APECS national committees, and early career researchers and professionals from around the world have benefitted from her generous donation of time and sharing of her expertise. She is also a masterful creator of networks, not only amongst APECS members but the entire global polar community. Furthermore, not only is she a high-profile woman in polar science, but Renuka has also been open about the challenges she has faced throughout her career while remaining an outspoken advocate for members of underrepresented communities.

The nomination letters emphasized that she “never hesitates to provide support whether it is through her professional position or personal engagement”. Her “mentorship has been anything but passive. She has consistently gone out of her way to ensure that my voice is heard in professional settings as well as become a true friend - one of the few people I know that I can call upon at any hour, with any professional or academic concern, and she'll be there with a compassionate ear and thoughtful advice". The nominators also highlighted Renuka’s “talent for identifying someone’s research interests and priorities, and introducing them to leaders in the field, with a suggestion of how they may be able to mutually assist one another”. She is “a strong advocate for early career researchers, [who] helps to push our work to the forefront even when we might lack the confidence to do so”.

On behalf of all APECS members, we would like to sincerely thank Hugues and Renuka for everything that they have done as mentors for both our organisation and so many of us as individuals. We are honored to present the 2017 APECS International Mentorship Award to them both as a small token of our enormous gratitude for their time, wisdom, and passion.

Thank you also to the work of the APECS International Mentorship Award 2017 Committee from the APECS Council: Alice Bradley, Julie Bull, Jennifer Cooper, Meagan Dewar, Jose Queiros, Alexander Thornton, Gerlis Fugmann (ex-officio).

5.4. Projects from the APECS National Committees

Project	Description
APECS Belgium	
APECS Belgium at SCAR Biology Symposium 2017	<p>Low Fare Accommodation: Together with organizers of the SCARBio17, APECS Belgium helped manage low fare accommodation for ECRs attending the conference (see some details here). This is a possibly under-appreciated activity (quite work intensive, but not much recognition, except from people that actually use it). Despite some difficulties they received generally positive feedback from the ECRs that could use this opportunity. APECS Organizers: Charène Guillaumot, Franz M. Heindler & Henrik Christiansen</p> <p>ECR Awards: Together with the APECS International Directorate (Gerlis Fugmann) and conference organizers, APECS Belgium organized the early career presentation & poster awards at the conference. Six awards were given to four female and two male ECRs. Prizes included certificates, book(s), scarf/tie, and t-shirt. APECS Organizers: Gerlis Fugmann, Antonio Aguera, Camille Moreau, Quentin Jossart, Charène Guillaumot, Henrik Christiansen & many, many volunteers.</p> <p>Antarctic Photo Auction: APECS Belgium ordered printouts of the succeeding pictures of our photo competition. These were displayed during the conference and offered for sale in a “pen and paper auction”. The surplus will serve as support for future APECS Belgium activities. Organizers: Franz M. Heindler & Henrik Christiansen</p> <p>Social Evening: APECS Belgium organized a meeting point for ECRs (& friends) in a local pub on Tuesday evening and sponsored the first round of drinks with left-over money from the workshop to kickstart socializing outside of the official conference program. Without much effort this was quite successful as the chosen bar became a regular meeting point also on following evenings. Organizers: Franz M. Heindler & Henrik Christiansen</p>
APECS Brazil	
Antártica ou Antártida?	Free Distance Learning Course developed by APECS-Brazil and Federal University of ABC to teachers of elementary schools.
APECS Canada	
<u>APECS-ASA Mentor Award</u>	APECS Canada and the ArcticNet Student Association (ASA) work together each year to present the APECS-ASA Mentor Award. In 2016, it was awarded to Joel McAlister. award given at ArcticNet 2016 to Joel McAlister (Environment and Natural Resource Technology Senior Instructor at Aurora College, Canada)

	APECS-Canada representative on the Multi-stakeholder Review Committee (MSRC) that reviewed and scored research fund applications for the Polar Knowledge Canada 2017-18 grants.
APECS France	
<u>Les Savanturiers</u>	APECS France is currently working with the CRI (Center of Interdisciplinary research) about a project called "Les Savanturiers". Throughout the year, they link researchers and classrooms in order to plan research projects. The researchers take a few hours per month and help the students to learn about polar regions and to think about an experiment they can do at school. This year, the CRI asked APECS France to participate to a <u>MOOC (online courses) about linking research and education</u> . In line with the MOOC, five members were offered to animate an online platform to help teachers understanding the basics of the MOOC.
Survival training course in the Alps	A new project offered to APECS France members is the survival training: a day course in the Alps with a mountain guide in order to learn a few basics for surviving in a cold and harsh environment and deal with working on a glacier. Two first courses will take place in September.
Mercredi soir aux pôles	Spring 2017, we started organising the "Mercredi soir aux pôles" (Wednesday night in the Poles) - an online conference happening every Wednesday night, once a month. The topics range from glaciology to biology and geopolitics and any member can have access to the conference.
APECS Germany	
<u>APECS Germany support for the "Adopt a buoy" program</u>	(organised by Sea ice physics, AWI Bremerhaven)
APECS Russia	
	Research activities Under the leadership of Dr. P.Konstantinov the large scientific network UHIARC - "Urban Heat Island Research Campaign in the Arctic" has been developed since 2015 and operates nowadays in Apatity (Murmansk region) and 5 other Russian Arctic cities. This activity opened to international scientific community an opportunity for a comprehensive study of the typical polar UHI combining dense in-situ observations, satellite remote sensing data and climate change in urban areas in the Arctic zone.
	Lectures and seminars for school kids of different ages are taking place around the world with the support and participation of national committee members. Among them are: lectures and national scientific contests for school students in Russia (Kola Peninsula and Moscow regions), an <u>online seminar</u> for school kids in South Africa, CAFF of The Arctic Council initiative in disseminating educational materials on Arctic research among local schools, the project " <u>Scientists in the classroom</u> ".

Webinar project	<p>Online science communication and outreach activities are mostly highlighted with the <i>webinar project</i> run by Katya Uryupova and Yulia Zaika. In 1,5 year we have organised a total of 19 webinars covering various research topics, have presented the outcomes of the media and outreach project at 2 large international conferences, and prepared a research paper on the project management. Moreover, a database of Russian polar researchers has been created. The videos from webinars are available here.</p>
<p>Polar Initiative (Russia)</p>	
Guidebook for the “Polar” Arkhangelsk	<p>The polar guidebook for Arkhangelsk was specially prepared by Russian researches on the basis of Russian State Museum of the Arctic and Antarctic (RSMAA, Saint Petersburg) for Forum and Youth Conference participants. It is available here. Today, the online polar guidebook for Arkhangelsk is available in 1.0 version and comprises information on monuments and sights related to Arctic researches and the North Pole and Russian North exploration and development. It includes facts about Arkhangelsk museums, streets named after heroic polar explorers, scientists, and artists. The guidebook is made on the basis of Yandex interactive maps. Guide compilers hope that there will be improvements made by citizens and Forum participants to add to the 2.0 version. The project is managed the Russian Polar Initiative and RSMAA.</p>
<p>UK Polar Network</p>	
Sounds of Change	<p>During the recent British Antarctic Survey workshop in Cambridge the UKPN facilitated a competition for a polar science outreach proposal. The project "Sounds of Change: Greenland Ice Sheet Melt" was picked for its original idea. We wish to congratulate Heather Bell (Durham University), Joseph Nolan (Netherlands Organisation for Scientific Research), and Zuzanna Swirad (Durham University) for this achievement and we are looking forward to support their efforts realising the proposed project. More information available here.</p>

6. Partners and Sponsors

6.1. APECS Formal Partnerships (MoUs)

APECS has formal partnerships through MoUs with the following organisations and institutions:

- Alfred Wegener Institute Helmholtz Centre for Polar and Marine Research (AWI)
- Arctic Frontiers
- Arctic Research Consortium of the United States (ARCUS)
- European Polar Board (EPB)
- International Arctic Science Committee (IASC)
- International Association of Arctic Social Scientists (IASSA)
- International Association of Cryospheric Sciences (IACS)
- International Glaciological Society (IGS)
- International Network for Terrestrial Research and Monitoring in the Arctic (INTERACT)
- International Permafrost Association (IPA)
- Murmansk Arctic State University (MASU)
- Permafrost Young Researchers Network (PYRN)
- Polar Educators International (PEI)
- Scientific Committee on Antarctic Research (SCAR)
- University of the Arctic
- UiT The Arctic University of Norway

These groups often provide in-kind support in the form of advertising, high-level endorsement, meeting space at conferences, and travel support for APECS members.

In addition, APECS works with many other Polar-research focused institutions and organizations around the world without a formal agreement. We want to thank all of our partners for their contributions for supporting early career researchers and APECS.

6.2. Sponsors

For our international activities, APECS has received in 2016-2017 support from the organizations, institutions and projects below. Thank you from the entire APECS leadership for helping us “Shape the Future of Polar Research” over the last year and in the years to come!

6.2.1. APECS International Directorate Sponsors

The main costs associated with running APECS comes in supporting our International Directorate Office with its staff members. We are very grateful for our International Directorate funders for providing the finances needed to keep all our activities centrally coordinated and running efficiently. During the **2016-2017** term, the host and sponsors of the APECS International Directorate office changed:

a) Main location

From **2009 until February 2017** the main APECS International Directorate was located in **Tromsø, Norway** hosted at UiT The Arctic University of Norway and funded with one full-time staff member (Executive Director) as well as office and travel costs for the office by the Research Council of Norway, UiT The Arctic University of Norway and the Norwegian Polar Institute.

The Research Council
of Norway

From **February 2017 until January 2022**, the APECS International Directorate Office will be funded through the generous support of the Alfred Wegener Institute, Helmholtz Center for Polar and Marine Research and hosted at AWI Research Centre in **Potsdam, Germany**. The office funding includes one full-time APECS Executive Director, one part-time APECS Administrative Assistant as well as office and travel costs for the office.

ALFRED-WEGENER-INSTITUT
HELMHOLTZ-ZENTRUM FÜR POLAR-
UND MEERESFORSCHUNG

b) Additional support and project offices

From **July 2016 until February 2017**, the Murmansk Arctic State University funded an additional part-time APECS Officer for the APECS International Directorate located in Murmansk, Russia.

From **October 2017 until spring 2020**, UiT The Arctic University of Norway hosts an additional APECS Project Officer at its Faculty of Biosciences, Fisheries and Economics in **Tromsø, Norway**. The position is funded through the two **EU Horizon 2020 projects INTERACT (International Network for Terrestrial Research and Monitoring in the Arctic)** and **APPLICATE (Advanced Prediction in Polar regions and beyond: modelling, observing system design and Linkages associated with a Changing Arctic climaTE)** and is responsible for coordinating the UiT and APECS tasks as part of these two projects, and helping with other activities in the APECS International Directorate. UiT also funds some travel support for the APECS Executive Director for managing and supervising the two projects.

Co-funded by the Horizon 2020 programme
of the European Union

6.2.2. Event and other support

APECS wants to specifically acknowledge the financial support by **Antarctic Science Ltd.** for Antarctic activities within APECS.

We also acknowledge **Arctic Portal** in Akureyri, Iceland for continuous in-kind website support for and hosting of the APECS website.

Travel support was provided for APECS leaders / representatives and other early career researchers to attend various meetings and events by several organisations and institutions including, but not limited to:

- **Climate and Cryosphere (CliC) Project** for travel to the CliC SSC Meeting 2017
- **German SCAR / IASC Committee** for travel of an APECS representative to attend their meeting
- **Nordnorsk Vitensenteret (Science Centre of Northern Norway)** in Tromsø for funding for Arctic Frontiers Science for Schools providing travel support for 3 early career researchers to present at the event.

6.2.3. Support from APECS for APECS activities

Despite having only a small budget, APECS was able to support with small amounts several of its activities:

- APECS Executive Committee Meeting 2017 in Prague, Czech Republic (April 2017)
- Prizes for the APECS Online Conference 2017
- Prizes for the APECS International Polar Week Photo Contest 2017
- Prizes for the Antarctica Day 2017 Photo Contest
- Prizes for the APECS International Polar Week FrostBytes Contest 2017
- As well as workshops and activities organized by APECS Portugal, APECS Finland, APECS Italy, Indian Polar Research Network (IPRN), APECS Oceania and APECS Italy

6.3. Partners and Sponsors of the APECS National Committees

Several APECS National Committees were able to get financial and in-kind support for their activities (workshops, outreach events, etc.) from various national sponsors, including, but not limited to:

APECS Belgium

Partners:

- **Belgian National Committee for Antarctic Research (BNCAR)**: two APECS Belgium representative at BNCAR (H. Christiansen & A. Gossart), who regularly attend BNCAR's meetings ([see e.g.](#))
- **Belgian Science Policy Office (BELSPO)**: mostly support for infrastructure (meetings can take place there including further in-kind support) but in past some financial support
- **Royal Belgian Institute of Natural Sciences (RBINS)**

Sponsors: APECS NL/BE Symposium 2016 was supported by APECS NL in-kind support (which comes from NWO – The Netherlands Organisation for Scientific Research). Other APECS Belgium meetings can be supported in-kind by BELSPO (Belgian Science Policy Office), although we didn't use this opportunity during the last term. The APECS Workshop at SCARBio17 was supported by SCAR Organization AntEco and SCADM (Scientific Committee on Antarctic Research (SCAR) "State of the Antarctic Ecosystem" and SCAR Standing Committee on Antarctic Data Management; 500 US Dollars each) and Laboratory of Biodiversity and Evolutionary Genomics, KU Leuven (in-kind). Further SCARBio17 activities were supported by the Conference Organization, which provided in-kind support and paid for half of the amount of the pictures (408 Euros).

APECS Brazil

Partners: **Colégio Maria Auxiliadora**, Rede Notre Dame, Rio Grande do Sul, Brazil (UNESCO Associated School)

APECS Canada

Partners: **Polar Knowledge Canada** - providing advice and recommendations for student internship candidates and membership on the Science and Technology Advisory Committee; **ArcticNet Student Association** (for APECS-Canada-ASA Mentor Award and ArcticNet Student Day)

Sponsors: **Yukon Science Institute** and the **Beringia Centre** (space for Polar Film Fest Watch Party), **Nunavut Arctic College** (in-kind - space for film night and poster session, printing posters), **Haines Junction Mountain Festival** (booth space)

APECS Chile

Partners: **Chilean Antarctic Institute (INACH)** - help with visualization in social platforms and publication of some press notes and articles for a non-scientific journal; **Universidad Alberto Hurtado** - release of press note for APECS Chile legal status confirmation.

APECS France

Partners: **CRI (Center of Interdisciplinary research)** for the project "[Les Savanturiers](#)"

Sponsors: The prize awarded by the Yves Rocher Foundation will contribute to the organization of the 2016 Polar Week events.

APECS Germany

Sponsors: DFG (German Research Foundation) - travel support; German Priority Program for Antarctic Research (SPP 1158) - in-kind support (logistics and refreshments); PYRN (Permafrost Young Researchers Network)

Indian Polar Research Network

Partners: [Wildlife Institute of India](#), Department of Geology, [University of Delhi](#), [National Centre for Antarctic and Ocean Research](#)

Sponsors: Wildlife Institute of India, Department of Geology, University of Delhi, National Centre for Antarctic and Ocean Research - all of these have contributed in financial as well as in-kind sponsorship.

APECS Netherlands

Sponsors: Netherlands Organisation for Scientific Research (NWO)

APECS Oceania

Sponsors: in-kind sponsorship from Monash University for catering of our Symposium in September 2017

APECS Portugal

Partners: PROPOLAR - Portuguese Polar Programme

Sponsors: PROPOLAR (Portuguese Polar Programme) help APECS Portugal in ensuring a location for the workshop, although there were no monetary help this year.

Polar Initiative (Russia)

Partners: 46 MoU with research institutes and universities

Sponsors: Have sponsors from private mentors

APECS Sweden

Sponsors: Our funding is provided via a Funding for networking activities by the Swedish Polar Research Secretariat

APECS Switzerland

Sponsors: Swiss Federal Institute for Forest, Snow and Landscape Research (WSL), Swiss snow, ice and permafrost society, Swiss Academy of Sciences

UK Polar Network

Partners: Foreign Commonwealth Office, International Polar Foundation, British Antarctic Survey, NERC Arctic Office

Sponsors: Foreign Commonwealth Office/British Antarctic Territory grant (financial)

APECS United States (USAPECS)

Partners: ARCUS, NASA, NSF, and IGS for their formal and informal support of our activities.

Sponsors: ARCUS has been inviting USAPECS to their AGU reception for the past two years. NASA and NSF are funding the Polar SciComm workshop in Boulder this summer (August 2017). We've also had regular events at International Glaciological Society symposia, and they are helping with application review and workshop logistics for the SciComm workshop this summer.

6.4. International Opportunities for APECS members in 2016-2017

Committee / Organization / Conference	Name	Affiliation
Early Career Researchers on International Committees <i>*indicates APECS representative)</i>		
Created new in 2016-2017:		
<u>International Scientific Steering Committee of POLAR2018</u>	Ruth Vingerhagen*	University of Cambridge, United Kingdom
<u>International Arctic Science Committee (IASC) Fellowship Programme 2017</u>	Manisha Ganeshan (Atmosphere WG)	Universities Space Research Association (United States)
	Shridhar Jawak (Cryosphere WG)	National Centre for Antarctic & Ocean Research, Earth System Science Organization (ESSO), Ministry of Earth Sciences, Govt. of India, India
	Thomas Armitage (Marine WG)	University College London (United Kingdom) / NASA Jet Propulsion Laboratory (United States)
	Violetta Gassiy (Social and Human WG)	Kuban State University (Russia)
	Alevtina Evgrafova (Terrestrial WG)	University of Bern (Switzerland)
INTERACT Transnational Access Evaluation Board 2017-2018	Heather Mariash*	National Wildlife Research Centre, Canada
SCAR Past Antarctic Ice Sheet Dynamics (PAIS) Steering Committee	Mathieu Casado*	LSCE and LIPhy, France
	Adam Campbell	Otago University, New Zealand
	Pamela Santibanez	Instituto Antartico Chileno, Chile
SCAR Capacity Building, Education and Training (CBET) Advisory Group	Hanne Nielsen*	University of Tasmania, Australia
	Alexander Thornton*	University of Alaska Fairbanks, United States
	Gabriela Roldan*	University of Canterbury, New Zealand
Arctic Biodiversity Congress	Gerlis Fugmann*	APECS International Directorate / Alfred Wegener Institute, Helmholtz Center for Polar and Marine Research, Germany
Arctic Change 2017 International Steering Committee	Gerlis Fugmann*	APECS International Directorate / Alfred Wegener Institute, Helmholtz Center for Polar and Marine Research, Germany

Longer-term representation continuing in 2016-2017:

<u>Scientific Committee on Antarctic Research (SCAR) Life Sciences (LS) Scientific Standing Group (SSG)</u>	Fernanda Quaglio	Universidade Estadual Paulista, Brazil
	Jeff Bowman	Lamont-Doherty Earth Observatory, United States
	Henrik Christiansen	KU Leuven, Belgium
Scientific Committee on Antarctic Research (SCAR) Expert Group on Birds and Marine Mammals (EG BAMM)	Jaimie Cleeland	University of Tasmania, Australia
ISMALSS (Ice Sheet Mass Balance and Sea Level) Steering Committee	Ellyn Enderlin*	University of Maine, USA
SCAR Astronomy & Astrophysics in Antarctica (AAA) Steering Committee	Jennifer Cooper	Cornell University, USA
Polar Prediction Project Steering Group	Jonathan Day*	University of Reading, UK
SCAR Antarctic Climate Change in the 21 st Century (AntClim21) Steering Committee	Alia Khan*	University of Colorado Boulder, USA
Arctic Frontiers International Steering Committee	Gerlis Fugmann*	APECS International Directorate / Alfred Wegener Institute, Helmholtz Center for Polar and Marine Research, Germany

Early Career Researchers at International Meetings and Workshops

*represented APECS as invited observer at the meeting

**attended as invited early career researchers

CAFF Board Meeting Longyearbyen, Svalbard; 6-8 September 2016	Karolina Paquin*	
EU PolarNet Town Hall Event Brussels, Belgium; 27 September 2016;	Henrik Christiansen*	KU Leuven, Belgium
INTERACT Kick-off Meeting 2017 Keflavik, Iceland; 24 - 26 January 2017;	Gerlis Fugmann*	APECS International Directorate / UiT The Arctic University of Norway, Norway
APPLICATE Kick-off Meeting 2017 Bremerhaven, Germany; 7 - 9 February 2017;	Gerlis Fugmann*	APECS International Directorate / Alfred Wegener Institute, Helmholtz Center for Polar and Marine Research, Germany
13th CliC Scientific Steering Group Meeting Wellington, New Zealand; 17 - 18 February 2017	Christian Wild*	University of Canterbury, New Zealand
IASC Council Meeting 2017 Prague, Czech Republic; 2 April 2017;	Alice Bradley* Gerlis Fugmann*	Dartmouth College, United States APECS International Directorate / Alfred Wegener Institute, Helmholtz Center for Polar and Marine Research, Germany
European Polar Board Meeting Prague, Czech Republic; 31 March 2017	Gerlis Fugmann*	APECS International Directorate / Alfred Wegener Institute, Helmholtz Center for Polar and Marine Research, Germany

<p><u>26th Annual Meeting of the German National Committee SCAR / IASC Meeting 2017</u> Cologne, Germany; 8 - 9 June 2017</p>	<p>Andreas Preusser</p>	<p>University of Trier, Germany</p>
<p>Potsdam Summer School Potsdam, Germany; 7 September 2017,</p>	<p>Gerlis Fugmann*</p>	<p>APECS International Directorate / Alfred Wegener Institute, Helmholtz Center for Polar and Marine Research, Germany</p>

Poster awards (co-)coordinated by APECS

<p><u>Arctic Frontiers 2017 Early Career Poster Awards</u> 28 January 2017 Tromsø, Norway</p>	<p>Overall winner: Katalin Blix (UiT Arctic University of Norway) for the poster "Monitoring primary productivity through Chlorophyll-a content estimation in the Arctic."</p> <p>Winner Part I: Oliver Müller (University of Bergen, Norway) for the poster "How permafrost organic matter input in an Arctic fjord alters the bacterial community structure."</p> <p>Winner Part II: Sarah Holmes (University of Exeter, UK) for the poster "Using annually resolved bivalve records and biogeochemical models to understand and predict climate impacts on coastal oceans."</p> <p>Winner Part III/IV: Laura Wheeland (Center for Fisheries and Ecosystem Research, Newfoundland, Canada) for the poster "Inshore fisheries resources, biogeography and oceanography: Insight from sampling aboard platforms of opportunity in the Canadian Arctic."</p>
<p><u>Early Career Poster Awards at the Arctic Science Summit Week 2017</u> April 2017 Prague, Czech Republic</p>	<p>Elena Kharyutkina (Atmosphere): Tendencies in Current Climate Change and Atmospheric Circulation Variability in the Arctic Region of West Siberia</p> <p>Erlend Knudsen (Cryosphere): Observational Evidence for Predictive Skills from Arctic Summer Sea Ice Extent</p> <p>Diana Mastracci (Cross-Cutting) "'Hacking" Traditional Knowledge Based Solutions to Climate Change. The NASA "Sea-Ice" App Challenge"</p> <p>Alex Thornton (Marine and Overall Winner): "Using Pacific Walrus Teeth to Study Patterns of Change in Alaska Food Web Dynamics"</p> <p>Anna Bobrik (Terrestrial) "Carbon Efflux and Soil Carbon Storage: Transect from Taiga to Tundra of Western Siberia</p> <p>Yana Korneeva (Social & Human) "The model of psychological safety of oil and gas shift workers in the Arctic"</p>